

Transport equation for Ultra-High Energy neutrino events

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AstroParticles at Ultra-High Energies (UHE)

UHE: $E > 100 \text{ TeV}$

At UHE, Universe is transparent for neutrinos

Diffuse flux of astrophysical neutrinos from IceCube

(and an 'anomalous' UHE event from KM3NeT)

Neutrino Telescope Collaborations provide **effective area**

$$\left\langle \frac{dN_{\text{sign}}}{dt dE_{\nu} d\Omega_{\nu}} \right\rangle = \underline{A_{\text{eff}}^{\nu}(E_{\nu}, \Omega_{\nu})} \phi_{\nu}^{\oplus}(E_{\nu}, \Omega_{\nu})$$

Inclusive in muon energy (or other types of energy deposition)

Does not map directly to underlying physics – Not very useful for fits

Would require new MC run for each new case study

Experimental rate

$$\left\langle \frac{dN_\mu}{dt dE_\mu d\Omega_p} \right\rangle = \frac{\text{number of muons}}{\text{time} \times \text{energy} \times \text{solid angle}}$$

Match from a 'first principle' calculation

$$\langle N_\mu \rangle = \int_V d^3x \int \frac{d^3p}{(2\pi)^3} \underline{f_\mu(t, \vec{x}, \vec{p})}$$

Boltzmann/transport equation to compute the **distribution of muons**

The only unknown quantity is the flux (or distribution) of neutrinos

$$4\pi\phi_\nu = E_\nu^2 f_\nu v$$

Experimental rate

$$\left\langle \frac{dN_{\mu}}{dt dE_{\mu} d\Omega_p} \right\rangle = \frac{\text{number of muons}}{\text{time} \times \text{energy} \times \text{solid angle}}$$

Fully differential in muon energy
(or other types of energy deposition)

Control over all physics inputs

Can be applied to any physics case

Having efficiencies for event types would be useful

Transport equation

$$\frac{\partial f_\mu}{\partial t} + \dot{\vec{x}} \cdot \frac{\partial f_\mu}{\partial \vec{x}} + \dot{\vec{p}}_\mu \cdot \frac{\partial f_\mu}{\partial \vec{p}_\mu} = K(t, \vec{x}, \vec{p}_\mu)$$

Liouville's operator

Kernel, contains all interaction terms that can change the distribution:

- Weak interactions
- QED processes
- tau decays

$$K_{\text{scattering}}^{\nu\mu}(t, \vec{x}, \vec{p}_\mu) \equiv \int d^3 p_{\nu\mu} f_{\nu\mu}(t, \vec{x}, \vec{p}_{\nu\mu}) n_N(\vec{x}) v \frac{d\sigma(\nu_\mu N \rightarrow \mu \dots)}{d^3 p_\mu}$$

Transport equation

Input

Get an explicit solution

- Initial condition: $f_\mu(t, \vec{x} \in \oplus, \vec{p}_\mu) = 0$

- Muon/tau has continuous energy loss via QED processes with low q^2

- Much faster than weak interactions, leave muon direction unchanged

$$\dot{p} \approx -v \frac{dE_\ell}{dx} = -b_\ell v E_\ell$$

- Integrate along Line of Sight (LOS)

- At UHE, muon is so boosted it is always forward \rightarrow same trajectory as neutrino

Relevant scales

Neutrinos cannot travel the entire radius of Earth at UHE

Tau is 'long-lived'

$$\lambda_\tau \simeq 5 \text{ km} \left(\frac{E_\tau}{100 \text{ PeV}} \right)$$

Relevant scales

Leptons lose energy on 'small' scales

$$E_\ell(\xi) = E_\ell \exp[-b_\ell(L - \xi)]$$

In the SM, scales are all well separated

Support of integral is limited to a region of size $1/b$

Cross sectional Area of the experiment (approx as spherical)

Local density

Attenuation at detector

Effective radius

$$\left\langle \frac{dN}{dt dE_\mu d\Omega_p} \right\rangle_{\nu_\mu} \approx 4\pi A_{\text{disk}} n_N^{\text{near}} \sigma(E_\mu) \phi_\nu^\oplus(E_\mu) \exp\left(-\frac{L(\Omega_p)}{L_\nu(E_\mu)}\right) \left(R_{\text{det}} + \frac{1}{b_\mu}\right)$$

At this point...

We have an explicit solution for the muon distribution that

- Can be computed numerically
- Or even analytically (with some approximations)
- Can vary and infer flux inputs and physical parameters (in the backup slides)

Let's use it

IceCube - diffuse

Diffuse neutrino flux $\phi_\nu = \phi_0 \left(\frac{E_\nu}{100 \text{ TeV}} \right)^{-\gamma}$ No preferential direction

$$\left\langle \frac{dN}{dt dE_\mu d\Omega_p} \right\rangle_{\nu_\mu} \approx 4\pi A_{\text{disk}} n_N^{\text{near}} \sigma(E_\mu) \phi_\nu^\oplus(E_\mu) \exp\left(-\frac{L(\Omega_p)}{L_\nu(E_\mu)}\right) \left(R_{\text{det}} + \frac{1}{b_\mu}\right)$$

[IceCube 9.5y Data: 2111.10299]

Sanity check: our fit is consistent with IceCube results

$$\gamma_{\text{IC}} = 2.37 \pm 0.09$$

$$\gamma_{\text{ML}} = 2.46 \pm 0.05$$

Measured energy

$$E_{\mu} = 120_{-60}^{+110} \text{ PeV}$$

Inferred energy

$$E_{\nu} = 220_{-110}^{+570} \text{ PeV}$$

(with IC power-law as prior)

Inclination

$$\theta = (0.54 \pm 2.4)^{\circ}$$

IceCube vs KM3NeT - diffuse

Diffuse neutrino flux $\phi_\nu = \phi_0 \left(\frac{E_\nu}{100 \text{ TeV}} \right)^{-\gamma}$ No preferential direction

$$\left\langle \frac{dN}{dt dE_\mu d\Omega_p} \right\rangle_{\nu_\mu} \approx 4\pi A_{\text{disk}} n_N^{\text{near}} \sigma(E_\mu) \phi_\nu^\oplus(E_\mu) \exp\left(-\frac{L(\Omega_p)}{L_\nu(E_\mu)}\right) \left(R_{\text{det}} + \frac{1}{b_\mu}\right)$$

Ratio of expected events

$$\Delta \equiv \frac{\langle N_\mu \rangle_{\text{IC}}}{\langle N_\mu \rangle_{\text{KM3}}} \approx \left(\frac{[TA]_{\text{IC}}}{[TA]_{\text{KM}}} \right) \left(\frac{R_{\text{IC}} + b_\mu^{-1}}{R_{\text{KM}} + b_\mu^{-1}} \right) \sim 70$$

Not negligible level of tension

$$\Delta\sigma = 3.1$$

[Agrees with Li et al.:
2502.04508]

IceCube vs KM3NeT - diffuse

Diffuse neutrino flux

$$\phi_\nu = \phi_0 \left(\frac{E_\nu}{100 \text{ TeV}} \right)^{-\gamma}$$

No preferential direction

$$\Delta\sigma = 3.1$$

[Agrees with Li et al.:
2502.04508]

IceCube vs KM3NeT - point source

Point source $\phi_\nu = \phi_0 \left(\frac{E_\nu}{100 \text{ TeV}} \right)^{-\gamma} \delta^{(2)}(\Omega_\nu - \Omega_{\text{PS}}(t))$ Fixed direction in the sky

IceCube vs KM3NeT - point source

IceCube, $E_\nu = 1 \text{ EeV}$

IceCube is more sensitive to the source region inferred by KM3NeT

KM3NeT, $E_\nu = 1 \text{ EeV}$

Transparency averaged over 1 day

$$\langle D \rangle_{\text{IC}} \sim 0.99$$

$$\langle D \rangle_{\text{KM}} \sim 0.45$$

IceCube vs KM3NeT - point source

IceCube, $E_\nu = 1 \text{ EeV}$

IceCube is more sensitive to the source region inferred by KM3NeT

KM3NeT, $E_\nu = 1 \text{ EeV}$

$$\Delta_{PS} \sim 140$$

$$\Delta\sigma = 3.8$$

Even larger tension!

[Unlike Li et al.:
2502.04508]

IceCube vs KM3NeT - others?

If the source is a time transient, tension is reduced (Blazar flares?)

$$\Delta_{\text{transient}} \approx \frac{V_{\text{IC}}}{V_{\text{KM}}} \sim 11$$

BSM physics! For a point source, need to make larger distances more important

e.g. Heavy Neutral Leptons, but cannot evade present bounds

Most likely, KM3NeT has seen an over fluctuation

Unless it sees another one...

Conclusions

- We develop a first-principle calculation of muon events at UHE Neutrino Telescopes
- KM3NeT event seems in tension with IceCube data, only time will tell

Work in Progress

- Generalize to different observables (NC or BSM)
- Include 'higher order' energy loss (e.g. diffusion)
- Write a code to rule em all

Backups

IceCube

KM3NeT

Baikal-GVD

Location

South Pole

Mediterranean

Baikal Lake

Volume(*)

1 km³

0.15 km³

0.5 km³

Exposure(*)

12 years

0.789 years

5 years

Technology

Large body of water (ice) instrumented with PMTs
Cherenkov detector

(*)as of Feb 2023

IceCube

IceCube

Muon track

Energy deposition – 'bang'

$$f_{\mu}(t, \vec{x}, \vec{p}) = \int_0^{L_{x,p}} \frac{d\xi}{v} K(t(\xi), \vec{x}(\xi), \vec{p}(\xi))$$

$$f_\mu(t, \vec{x}, \vec{p}) = \int_0^{L_{x,p}} \frac{d\xi}{v} \int d^3 p_{\nu_\mu} D(\vec{x}(\xi), p_{\nu_\mu}) \frac{4\pi \phi_\nu^\oplus(\vec{p}_{\nu_\mu})}{E_{\nu_\mu}^2} \frac{d\sigma(p_\mu(\xi))}{d^3 p_\mu(\xi)} n_N(\vec{x}(\xi))$$

+ contribution from tau decays

Line of Sight

Find trajectories along which the differential equation becomes ordinary

Fix $\vec{p} = p\hat{n}_p$ and assume direction does not change

$$\begin{cases} dt/d\xi = 1/v \\ d\vec{x}/d\xi = \hat{n}_p \\ d\vec{p}/d\xi = -b_\mu(\xi)\vec{p} \end{cases} \implies \begin{cases} t(\xi) = t + (\xi - L_{x,p})/v \\ \vec{x}(\xi) = \vec{x} - (L_{x,p} - \xi)\hat{n}_p \\ \vec{p}(\xi) = p\hat{n}_p \exp\left(\int_\xi^{L_{x,p}} d\xi' b(\xi')\right) \end{cases}$$

Integrate the transport equation

$$f_\mu(t, \vec{x}, \vec{p}) = \int_0^{L_{x,p}} \frac{d\xi}{v} K \left(t + (\xi - L_{x,p})/v, \vec{x} - (L_{x,p} - \xi)\hat{n}_p, p\hat{n}_p \exp \left[\int_\xi^{L_{x,p}} d\xi' b(\xi') \right] \right)$$

$$f_\mu(t, \vec{x}, \vec{p}) = \int_0^{L_{x,p}} \frac{d\xi}{v} \int d^3 p_{\nu_\mu} D(\vec{x}(\xi), p_{\nu_\mu}) \frac{4\pi \phi_\nu^\oplus(\vec{p}_{\nu_\mu})}{E_{\nu_\mu}^2} \frac{d\sigma(p_\mu(\xi))}{d^3 p_\mu(\xi)} n_N(\vec{x}(\xi))$$

Neutrino transparency
(survival probability)

$$D(\vec{x}, E_\nu, \Omega_\nu) \equiv \frac{\phi_\nu(\vec{x}, E_\nu, \Omega_\nu)}{\phi_\nu^\oplus(E_\nu, \Omega_\nu)}$$

Neutrino flux

Neutrino scattering
cross section

Earth density
profile

Evaluated at muon
energy \rightarrow includes
muon energy loss

Earth density profile

One-Dimensional Preliminary Reference Earth Model (PREM)

[A. M. Dziewonski, D. L. Anderson: 1981]

Water equivalent distance

$$\Delta L_{\text{we}} = \frac{\rho_X}{\rho_{\text{water}}} \Delta L_X$$

Neutrino cross section

At UHE the Fermi approx starts to fail \rightarrow small Bjorken- x

$$x \lesssim \frac{M_W^2}{ys} = 3 \cdot 10^{-4} \left(\frac{100 \text{ PeV}}{E_\nu} \right) \left(\frac{0.1}{\langle y \rangle} \right)$$

Small x parametrization

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} xq(x) \simeq \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x\bar{q}(x) = x^{-\lambda}$$

Uncertainty from small x extraction of PDFs

Note 1: uncertainty could be reduced including small- x LHCb data

Note 2: at even higher energies the x sec will flatten (Froissart bound)

$$\sigma_{\nu N}^{\text{CC}}(E_\nu) = \sigma_0 \left(\frac{E_\nu}{E_0} \right)^\lambda = 1.48 \times 10^{-33} \text{ cm}^2 \times \left(\frac{E_\nu}{10 \text{ PeV}} \right)^\lambda$$

Distributions of x and y can be computed analytically

$$\frac{d\sigma_{\nu N}}{dy} \approx \frac{G_F^2 M_W^2}{\pi} \tilde{s}^\lambda \left(y^{\lambda-1} \frac{2 + y(y-2)}{1-\lambda} \right) \Gamma(2-\lambda) \Gamma(1+\lambda)$$

$$\frac{d\sigma_{\nu N}}{dx} \approx \frac{G_F^2 M_W^2}{x^{\lambda+1} \pi} \left[\frac{\zeta(2 + \zeta(3 + 2\zeta)) - 2(1 + \zeta)^2 \log(1 + \zeta)}{\zeta^2(1 + \zeta)} \right]$$

Neutrino mean free path

$$\lambda(E_\nu) = \frac{1}{n_N \sigma_{\text{tot}}(E_\nu)} \approx 1.2 \times 10^4 \text{ km} \left(\frac{10 \text{ PeV}}{E_\nu} \right)^\lambda$$

CC deplete the neutrino flux

NC repopulate it at lower energy

$$\frac{\partial \phi_\nu}{\partial \xi} = -\frac{1}{\lambda(E_\nu)} \left[\phi_\nu(\xi, E_\nu) - \int_0^1 \frac{dy}{1-y} \mathcal{P}(y) \frac{\sigma_{\text{NC}}}{\sigma_{\text{tot}}} \phi_\nu\left(\xi, \frac{E_\nu}{1-y}\right) \right]$$

Neutrino transparency

$$D(\xi, E_\nu) = \exp\left(-\int_0^\xi \frac{d\zeta}{L_\nu(\zeta, E_\nu)}\right) = \exp\left(-\frac{\xi_{\text{we}}}{L_\nu^{\text{water}}(E_\nu)}\right)$$

Consider only CC scattering
(true in the elastic limit)

At UHE experiments are blind
to opposite side of Earth

Energy loss

Ionization negligible at UHE

$$-\left\langle \frac{dE_\ell}{dx} \right\rangle = a_\ell(E_\ell) + b_\ell(E_\ell)E_\ell$$

Radiative energy loss

Bremsstrahlung

Pair production

DIS

Energy loss

Ionization
negligible at UHE

$$-\left\langle \frac{dE_\ell}{dx} \right\rangle = a_\ell \cancel{(E_\ell)} + b_\ell(E_\ell)E_\ell$$

Energy evolution

$$E_\ell(x) = E_{\ell,0} \exp(-b_\ell x)$$

Distance travelled

$$d = \frac{1}{b_\ell} \log \left(\frac{E_\ell^{\text{in}}}{E_\ell^{\text{out}}} \right)$$

Is the approximation of continuous energy loss valid?

$$E_\ell(x) = E_{\ell,0} \exp(-b_\ell x)$$

Energy loss per scattering

$$\nu = \frac{\Delta E}{E} \longrightarrow b_\ell = n_N \int_{\nu_{\min}}^1 d\nu \frac{d\sigma}{d\nu} \nu$$

If b is dominated by soft scattering, continuous approx is reasonable

$$b_\ell = n_N \left(\overset{\text{Soft}}{\int_{\nu_{\min}}^{\nu_{\text{cut}}} d\nu \frac{d\sigma}{d\nu} \nu} + \overset{\text{Hard}}{\int_{\nu_{\text{cut}}}^1 d\nu \frac{d\sigma}{d\nu} \nu} \right)$$

If b is dominated by soft scattering, continuous approx is reasonable

$$b_\ell = n_N \left(\overset{\text{Soft}}{\int_{\nu_{\min}}^{\nu_{\text{cut}}} d\nu \frac{d\sigma}{d\nu} \nu} + \overset{\text{Hard}}{\int_{\nu_{\text{cut}}}^1 d\nu \frac{d\sigma}{d\nu} \nu} \right)$$

Bremsstrahlung $\frac{d\sigma_{\text{brem}}}{d\nu} \propto \frac{1}{\nu}$

Pair production $\frac{d\sigma_{\text{pp}}}{d\nu} \propto \frac{1}{\nu^2}$

$$N(L) \approx 100 \left(\frac{n_N}{n_N^{\text{water}}} \right) \left(\frac{L}{3 \text{ km}} \right) \times \log \left(\frac{E_\mu}{100 \text{ PeV}} \right)$$

Choose cut such that number of hard scattering is 'small'

$$b_\ell = n_N \left(\overset{\text{Soft}}{\int_{\nu_{\min}}^{\nu_{\text{cut}}} d\nu \frac{d\sigma}{d\nu} \nu} + \overset{\text{Hard}}{\int_{\nu_{\text{cut}}}^1 d\nu \frac{d\sigma}{d\nu} \nu} \right)$$

$$N_{\text{hard}} (b_{\text{soft}}^{-1}) \leq 0.15 N_{\text{soft}} (b_{\text{soft}}^{-1})$$

$$\nu_{\text{cut}} \sim 10^{-2}$$

[Agrees with Lipari and Stanev, 91]

Relevant scales

In the SM, scales are all well separated

Effective area

$$A_{\text{eff}}(E_\nu, \Omega_\nu) = A_{\text{disk}} \int_0^{L(\Omega_{\vec{p}})} d\xi \int_{\Delta_{E_\mu} \otimes \Delta_{\Omega_{\vec{p}}}} dE_\mu d\Omega_{\vec{p}} \epsilon(E_\mu, \Omega_{\vec{p}}) \mathcal{T}(E_\mu, \Omega_{\vec{p}} | E_\nu, \Omega_\nu; \xi)$$

Statistical framework

Likelihoods are modeled with a Poissonian

$$\mathcal{P}(k|n) = \frac{n^k e^{-n}}{k!}$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{IC}} = \prod_{i=1}^{n_b} \mathcal{P} \left(N_{i,\text{obs}}^{\text{IC}} | N_{i,\text{exp}}^{\text{IC}}(\hat{\theta}) \right)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{KM}} = \mathcal{P} \left(N_{i,\text{obs}}^{\text{KM}} | N_{i,\text{exp}}^{\text{KM}}(\hat{\theta}) \right)$$

Bayes factor

$$B_{D_1/D_2} = \frac{\int \mathcal{L}_{D_2}(\hat{\theta}|M) \pi(\theta) d\hat{\theta}}{\int \mathcal{L}_{D_2}(\hat{\theta}|M) \pi_{\text{ref}_{D_1}}(\hat{\theta}) d\hat{\theta}}$$

$B \gg 1$ when the reference model cannot make sense of D_2
There is tension!

Prior of the 'Standard Model' to test against

Statistical framework

Likelihoods are modeled with a Poissonian

$$\mathcal{P}(k|n) = \frac{n^k e^{-n}}{k!}$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{IC}} = \prod_{i=1}^{n_b} \mathcal{P} \left(N_{i,\text{obs}}^{\text{IC}} | N_{i,\text{exp}}^{\text{IC}}(\hat{\theta}) \right)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{KM}} = \mathcal{P} \left(N_{i,\text{obs}}^{\text{KM}} | N_{i,\text{exp}}^{\text{KM}}(\hat{\theta}) \right)$$

Assume likelihoods are Gaussian \rightarrow Bayes factor is distributed as a χ^2 with d degrees of freedom

$$\Delta\sigma = \sqrt{2} \operatorname{erfc}^{-1} \left[Q \left(\frac{d}{2}; 2 \ln B \right) \right]$$

Clearly a bad assumption, but that's how we like it